

Is your OCR good enough? Probably so. An assessment of the impact of OCR quality on downstream tasks for Dutch texts

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We conduct an assessment of the impact of OCR quality in collections in Dutch, considering two tasks: document classification and document clustering via topic modelling. We find that for both topic modelling (using LDA) and document classification (using a variety of methods, including deep neural networks), working with an OCRed version of a corpus does not in general compromise results. On the contrary, it may sometimes lead to better results. While more work is needed, including on evaluating different datasets and methods, our results further confirm previous work in suggesting that the quality of existing OCR is often sufficient to apply machine learning techniques.

Methods and data

In order to assess the impact of OCR on downstream tasks, we use *extrinsic evaluation*: for each task, we compare the results of the same models on two different versions of the same corpora: on the one hand, the OCRed text, and on the other hand, a 'ground truth' version which is known to be correct, or close to. Our results are based on the following datasets:

1. [Historical newspapers from the IMPACT project](#).
2. [A selection of books from DBNL](#).

The two datasets differ in terms of the quality of their OCR; in particular, the DBNL dataset displays a lower OCR quality, on average. This can be seen in the figure below, which shows the distribution of a dictionary lookup score using historical dictionaries. This measure, while limited, has the benefit that it can be applied in the absence of a ground truth. All details, as well as more extensive evaluations, are provided in the [accompanying repository](#).

The distribution of the dictionary lookup score for the ground truth texts (blue) and OCRred texts (red). Left: IMPACT dataset; Right: DBNL dataset.

Topic modelling

Topic modelling is a [widely-used technique in digital humanities](#), as it allows to cluster documents and interpret such clusters via word probability distributions (the ‘topics’). We consider a popular technique, called [Latent Dirichlet Allocation](#) (or LDA), and use the IMPACT dataset provided by the KB (1). Our results suggest a strong similarity between the two topic models. Firstly, intrinsic evaluation using [topic coherence](#) yields similar results. Secondly, using topic matching and the Kullback-Leibler divergence (KL, a measure of the distance between two probability distributions, such as topics), we are able to effectively find a pairing of topics between the two models (ground truth and OCRred), suggesting that the two do not differ substantially. Lastly, the topic model trained on OCRred data is as stable in its document topic distributions as the one trained on ground truth.

Left: The distribution of the Kullback-Leibler divergence of the paired topics of a model trained on OCRred data and one on ground truth data (low KL means more similar distributions). Right: the distribution of the per-document topic entropy, considering the $V = \{500, 1000, 2000, 5000\}$ top words.

Document classification

We use the second dataset of Dutch literature (2) and consider the task of classifying the genre of a book, as given by the [DBNL catalog](#). Our results below report the accuracy of each model,

as evaluated on a held-out 20% of the dataset, while the remaining 80% has been used for training. We refer the reader to our repository for the details of preprocessing, model tuning and fitting. As it can be seen, the OCRed version of the dataset does not compromise results. On the contrary, and surprisingly, it often yields slightly better results than using the ground truth. The LSTM (recurrent) neural network architecture is the best performing model, with an accuracy of over 93% on the OCRed dataset, whereas the same architecture on the ground truth reached only 86% accuracy.

In conclusion, our results align with previous recent work [1,2] in suggesting that the quality of the OCR might often be sufficient to apply machine learning techniques and use the ensuing results. While encouraging, our results are also limited to small datasets made of historical texts in Dutch and have to be considered as preliminary.

Code and data

More details on the datasets we used can be found here:

https://github.com/Giovanni1085/KB_OCR_impact/wiki/Datasets.

The same repository also contains all the code necessary to replicate our results:

https://github.com/Giovanni1085/KB_OCR_impact.

The dataset is in Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4498186>.

As an aside, the datasets we used can be significantly improved via post-OCR correction (between 10 and 17% improvement, using different scores). Full results are [available online](#), for the methodology we used, see [3].

References

1. Hill, Mark J, and Simon Hengchen. 2019. "Quantifying the Impact of Dirty OCR on Historical Text Analysis: Eighteenth Century Collections Online as a Case Study." *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities* 34 (4): 825–43. <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqz024>.
2. Strien, Daniel van, Kaspar Beelen, Mariona Ardanuy, Kasra Hosseini, Barbara McGillivray, and Giovanni Colavizza. 2020. "Assessing the Impact of OCR Quality on Downstream NLP Tasks." In *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Agents and Artificial Intelligence*, 484–96. Valletta, Malta: SCITEPRESS - Science and Technology Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0009169004840496>.
3. Todorov, Konstantin and Giovanni Colavizza. 2020. "Transfer Learning for Historical Corpora: An Assessment on Post-OCR Correction and Named Entity Recognition". In F. Karsdorp, M. McGillivray, A. Nerghe, & M. Wevers (Eds.), *CHR 2020 : Computational Humanities Research 2020: Proceedings of the Workshop on Computational Humanities Research (CHR 2020)* : Amsterdam, the Netherlands, November 18-20, 2020 (pp.

310-339). (CEUR Workshop Proceedings; Vol. 2723). CEUR-WS.
<http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2723/long32.pdf>.